

Post-COVID Pandemic - A Change of Consumer Buying Behaviour Towards E-grocery Marts with Reference to Telangana State

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Abstract

Throughout this time, the COVID-19 epidemic has had a devastating impact on society, economies, and countries all over the world, having an impact on numerous economic sectors. Because it has squeezed every aspect of our lives, it has irrevocably altered consumer behaviour. For many of us, though, it has just sped up the adoption of already effective behaviours, including digitization in industries like retail, finance, and many others. These lockdowns have had a profound impact on business operations, consumer behaviour, and people's daily lives while the economy improves. The market has witnessed a stunning change in customer behaviour, along with an unmatched increase in e-commerce operations worldwide. Numerous government regulations, programs, and restrictions were the driving forces behind these changes. Nowadays, essential goods and services are available on digital platforms.

The present study is on the reasons why consumers are changing their supermarket buying behaviour was driven by the unexpected increase in online grocery shopping in specific to Telangana region. The majority of research has been on motivational variables; however, it has not taken into account modern aspects that have evolved as a result of the coronavirus epidemic. By utilizing newly-emerging buying incentives brought on by the coronavirus and analysing their effects on customers' desire to shop for groceries online, the current study closes a gap in the literature.

Keywords: Online Grocery Shopping, Online Purchase Behaviour, Post-Corona Virus Situation

1. Introduction

The study made an effort to comprehend how COVID19, a novel coronavirus illness, affected consumer purchasing habits. Foreign visitors reported increased cases of the new coronavirus disease in India during its early stages. Domestic travel by bus, train, and airplane increased the number of COVID-19 patient populations who tested positive. By a novel coronavirus disease, the Indian market is badly impacted. Consumer behaviour has abruptly changed during a lockdown. Early on, customers did not take the COVID-19 situation more seriously. The Indian government has taken preventative measures, and the news media has raised awareness of the problem. People are unsure, perplexed, and cautious during that time. The masses went to the market to buy the necessities when a national lockdown was imposed. Drugs, face masks, hand gloves, and hand sanitizers were among the items that sellers were black-marketing. Consumers felt scared and unsafe following the declaration of lockdown. The news from television and other forms of media significantly changed how people behaved. The public anticipated a shortage of necessities, so they hurried to the store to make purchases. To safeguard and care for the lives of customers and their workers during lockdown, online marketing companies ceased their services. Consumers at the time did not pay as much attention to particular brands of products. People are hesitating, perplexed, and

being cautious at that moment. People headed to the market to get the necessities after the country was placed on lockdown. In addition to selling medications, face masks, hand gloves, and sanitizers, sellers were also black-marketing necessities. Following the announcement of a lockdown, customers felt scared and unsafe. People's behaviour was significantly altered by the news reported on television and in other media. Customers raced to the market to make purchases after learning about the shortage of necessities. In order to safeguard the lives of customers and their employees during a lockdown, online marketing companies ceased their services.

As per several researches conducted by various organization found that after the pandemic, 75% of Indian customers modified their purchasing habits. Following the epidemic, the majority of customers across demographics and regions are redefining their values and making purchases based on considerations other than price and quality. When it comes to their buying behaviours and values, 71% of individuals in India who were polled after the pandemic have changed their minds. They have reevaluated their priorities in life and are now more intent than ever on pursuing their unique purpose. The 16th annual research report from Accenture states that this is having a direct impact on what, how, and why they buy. While only 7% of respondents reported that the pandemic's unprecedented experience had no effect on their values as buyers, another 22% of Indian consumers appear to have developing attitudes and purchasing habits. The C-Suite will be required to structure the entire organization around experience, guarantee that all elements of operations, such as marketing, selling, innovations, Market research, and customer service, and comprehend new consumer impulses in order to drive innovation and growth in a post-pandemic economy.

2. Literature Review

According to Ankur Kumar Rastogi (2010), online purchasing in India has a very promising future. In India, attitudes regarding online purchasing are improving. Customers can shop online anytime, anywhere, and with a variety of simple and secure payment methods. Customers can compare prices between products and internet retailers.

Channel for grocery shopping The various food shopping channels each provide their customers specific benefits; for example, traditional brick-and-mortar stores allow customers to evaluate products quickly and tangibly, get recommendations and individualized service from store staff, and experience instant pleasure (Grewal et al.,2004). As opposed to traditional grocery stores, which require customers to travel, transport products, and face time constraints, online grocery stores are valued primarily for this reason (Whaley et al.,2019). Additionally, online grocery shopping gives customers more access to product information and price comparisons, assisting them in securing the best deal, avoiding salesmen, and facilitating direct comparison of several attributes (ibid.). Retailers are making the switch to the full online experience.

Time savings is another advantage of online purchasing, according to Barnard and Menoe (2020), which is consistent with the earlier findings (Kumar and Thakur, 2016; Hanus, 2016). For instance, OS eliminates the need for traveling to the store and the time spent at the checkout (Kwek et al., 2010). However, time savings have not been identified as a significant factor that encourages customers to buy for food online (Robinson et al., 2007). However, a more recent study demonstrates that time saving does factor into certain customers' decisions, particularly households with little free time (Blitstein et al., 2020). Accordingly, Lindskog and Brege (2020) believe that time pressure or poverty is a significant aspect of consumer behaviour that aids in consumer segmentation.

3. Research Design & Method

An online survey was chosen as the data collection strategy to test the hypotheses presented in the previous section. The ability to collect responses quickly while allowing participants to complete the survey in a location of their choice, which was helpful given the Covid-19 constraints, is one of the main advantages of using online questionnaires (Serkan and Bougie, 2016). Participants were required to respond to 17 questions about their demographics, shopping motivations, perceived aspects of online grocery shopping, present behaviour, and goals for the future.

3.1. Sampling And Statistical Techniques

The respondents were chosen using a filtering question in the questionnaire because the study was intended for those who had experience shopping online. To quickly and efficiently reach a large number of people, the non-probability sampling method was adopted. For a two-week period, replies to the questionnaire were being accepted via a link shared on Facebook, Instagram, and LinkedIn. Any respondent using a device such as a laptop, PC, or mobile phone with an internet connection could access the questionnaire.

3.2. Data Source

The following sources of information were gathered to track consumer purchasing patterns after covid19

The primary data

The primary data were gathered using the following methods. Respondents were contacted via mobile devices for a talk to better understand their purchasing habits, and they were also requested to complete a Google Form-based questionnaire.

Observation

The authors of the paper conducted their own in-depth observations to comprehend how consumers behave.

Secondary Data

The following resources, which were used to gather secondary data, are the most beneficial Publications from the government.

Published papers and surveys pertaining to COVID-19 and consumer purchasing patterns.

Published sources included of articles from newspapers, magazines, and research papers

4. Objectives Of The Study

- (1) To understand the factors that are affecting consumer buying behaviour arisen in post-pandemic towards online grocery marts of Telangana region .
- (2) To determine whether the selected factors like convenience, variety of products and saving time, unavailability of product, Contamination risk of virus like elements will impact online purchase intentions
- (3) To analyse the influence of post-COVID-19 on the buying behaviour of the consumers towards e-grocery marts

4.1. Hypothesis Of The Study

- H0 = COVID-19 causes a pandemic condition, and significant factors that affect consumer behaviour after the pandemic phase are dependant.
- H1 = COVID-19 causes a pandemic condition, and significant factors influencing consumer behaviour following the pandemic phase are independent.

5. Scope

The authors of the article concentrated on how the coronavirus affected consumer purchasing habits (COVID-19). In this study, an effort was made to comprehend the numerous elements that influence consumers' purchasing decisions. The current study only addresses the pandemic situation brought on by COVID-19 and how consumer purchasing habits altered to include online grocery shopping after the outbreak.

6. Limitations of the Study

- (1) Due to a few constrains, the paper writers were unable to personally visit the clients; instead, they contacted the respondents by phone.
- (2) The study was limited to the COVID-19 disease and Telangana customer shopping patterns for E-groceries. The study's findings would have been more complete if additional factors, such as the state of the market, the demand and supply of products, the movement of goods, the legal implications of a lockdown, and the socioeconomic effects of disease, had been taken into account.
- (3) There is a potential of sampling inaccuracy and time is a key restriction.

7. Results And Discussion

Table 1: Post-pandemic Consumer Buying Behaviour Towards E-groceries

Response	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	29	82.85
No	06	17.15
Total	35	100

Source: Primary Data

According to the respondents' observations and discussions, 82.85% of respondents acknowledged that the COVID-19 epidemic had a negative impact on their purchasing decisions. Research revealed that the diversity of items, convenience, time savings, risk of contamination, and other variables led to a quick change in customer purchasing behaviour.

Table 2: Factor Of Convenience Lead To Change In Consumer Behaviour Towards Online E-grocery Purchases

Response	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	26	74.28
No	9	25.71
Total	35	100

Source: Primary Data

The data in the previous table revealed the proportion of respondents who said that, in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic, online grocery shopping was convenient. Following the pandemic, convenience had a significant impact on consumers' purchasing decisions, according to 74.28% of survey respondents.

Table 3: Factor Of Availability Of Variety Of Products Lead To Change In Consumer Behaviour Towards Online E-grocery Purchases

Response	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	28	80.00
No	7	20.00
Total	35	100

Source: Primary Data

According to the respondents' observations and discussions, 80.00% of respondents acknowledged that the post-COVID-19 epidemic had a positive impact on their purchasing decisions through online due to availability of variety of products. Research revealed that the diversity of items, and other variables led to a quick change in customer purchasing behaviour.

Table 4: Factor Of Saving Time Lead To Change In Consumer Behaviour Towards Online E-grocery Purchases

Response	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	31	88.57
No	4	11.42
Total	35	100

Source: Primary Data

According to the respondents' observations and discussions, 88.57% of respondents acknowledged that the post-COVID-19 epidemic had a positive impact on their purchasing decisions through online due to time saving for selection and travelling. Research revealed that the Saving of time , and other variables led to a quick change in customer purchasing behaviour.

Table 5: Factor Of Unavailability Of Product Lead To Change In Consumer Behaviour Towards Online E-grocery Purchases

Response	No of Respondents	Percentage
Yes	18	51.42
No	17	48.57
Total	35	100

Source: Primary Data

According to the respondents' observations and discussions, 51.42% of respondents acknowledged that the post-COVID-19 epidemic had a minimal impact on their purchasing decisions through online due to unavailability of product. Research revealed that the unavailability of product led to a minimal impact or change in customer purchasing behaviour.

Table 6: Factor Of Risk Of Contamination And Spread Lead To Change In Consumer Behaviour Towards Online E-grocery Purchases

Response	No of Respondents	Percentage
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Yes	33	94.22
No	2	05.78
Total	35	100

Source: Primary Data

According to the respondents' observations and discussions, 94.22% of respondents acknowledged that the post-COVID-19 epidemic had a high impact on their purchasing decisions through online due to risk of contamination and spread. Research revealed that the risk of contamination and spread led to a high impact or change in customer purchasing behaviour.

According to the above table, only 5% of respondents willing continue to buy their groceries offline, while the other 95% of respondents prefer online shopping. It demonstrated how strongly consumers' post-pandemic ideas and attitudes were held. Customers readily accepted. Due to considerations such as a lack of supplies, convenience, the risk of contamination, and time savings, services are becoming more digital. Restrictions on the movement of non-essential items substantially hindered India's trade in goods throughout shutdown phases 1.0, 2.0, and 3.0.

8. Findings, Suggestions And Conclusions

- (1) Researchers discovered that throughout the period of the country's lockdown, online retailers like Flipkart, Amazon, Bigbasket, Dmart, and others expanded their services to keep and preserve social distance while also offering consumers a wide range of E services.
- (2) It was discovered during the research that post-pandemic customer behaviour toward E-groceries had significantly changed.
- (3) The research revealed that various elements, including a lack of supplies, comfort, the risk of contamination, and time savings, had an impact on customers' purchasing decisions in post-pandemic conditions.
- (4) It was also discovered that the government has made an effort to widen communication channels to raise consumer awareness.

9. Suggestions

- (1) E-grocery stores should offer their services even in remote areas, and they should create user-friendly local language apps.
- (2) Consumers shouldn't rely on rumours because they can cause consumers to hesitate when making

purchases online.

- (3) Consumers should not be defrauded by online hacking because payment gates should be closely watched.

10. Conclusions

The goal of this study was to determine whether Covid-19 resulted in the appearance of fresh motivating elements that would improve consumers' desire to shop for groceries online. This main research issue was addressed by establishing a number of hypotheses, which were either accepted or rejected in the results section based on the available online shopping literature and contemporary factors. Product scarcity, waiting times, and contamination risk are three characteristics that changed or occurred as a result of Covid-19 in the context of online grocery purchasing, according to the research. In addition. Surprisingly, out of the three existing criteria, only convenience was found to be relevant in our sample. Convenience, waiting time, and contamination risk were all found to have a beneficial impact on customers' purchasing decisions overall.

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